

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Eze**FIRST NAME:** Justice**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text

1. Early preparation for essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-2)
2. Citing verbatim quotes, Turabian style (EUCLID 2019, 7)
3. Consistency of focus (EUCLID, 2019, 14)
4. Usage Conventions (EUCLID 2019, 27)
5. Syntax and Grammar (EUCLID 2019, 29-35)
6. Italicization (EUCLID 2019, 47-48)
7. Page numbering (EUCLIDE 2019, 50)

RESPONSE PAPER 1 – WRITING EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing can be a daunting task, but an effective coaching from the very beginning of the program of study can be of immense help in navigating this arduous journey. The ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack for Period 1 proved to be that immense help. This nine-chapter PDF text from the very beginning introduced the reader to methods of writing qualitative essay. Among others, it emphasized the importance of starting the essay early. This included thinking through the topic and making sure that the key idea of the topic is focused on (EUCLID 2019, 1-13).

Overall, the coursepack appears to be an invaluable piece of information. Beyond detailing the expectations for doctoral level writing, it also provides insights into its level of intensity. Even though a few of the things in it were already known to me the coursepack was eye opening. There are aspects of it that stood out to me. This response paper will highlight those aspects of the coursepack that stood out to me as I read them.

2) REACTION TO THE COURSEPACK

Researching essay topic using various web and library sources is suggested. Although one may have an idea about the meaning of a given topic, it is not enough to write an essay based on independent thinking. An academic writer must be aware of what has been covered previously on a given topic so that he/she can bring new ideas to the fray without repeating what had been done. Consequently, the coursepack dwelt abundantly on discouraging plagiarism, which it defined as using “a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5).

To identify originality and discourage plagiarism, scholarly writing styles and citation methods were created. The coursepack discussed a few citation styles from various academic disciplines, such as, Chicago (Turabian), APA, MLA, and WHO. Along with proper citation, appropriate parsing and good grammar based on the country or regional usage (SAE or SBE) were among topics covered. Furthermore, a section of the coursepack provided table of Latin abbreviations and terms used in academic writing and the implications for their use.

Consequently, there are sample writings and usages of abbreviations and styles provided in form of edited documents to assist students see the application of these in academic writing. As these abbreviations were spelled out, they took a new meaning to me, and this was the first time I truly saw the complete words of some of these abbreviations. Furthermore, the illustrated essays provided practical lesson for proper use of grammar. A standalone, though important, part of the coursepack was served in a video clip about use of Zotero to ease a writer’s work of applying various styles to writing as well as creating a bibliography. I am still struggling with adopting Zotero for my writing. Although I downloaded the two sections mentioned, it still does not appear on my word page. Hopefully, I will get a mastery of it in time.

Notably, the following three discussions from the coursepack cleared up some misconceptions/controversies I have pondered over the years.

a) Spacing After a Period

The coursepack cleared all doubts about how many spaces to add using a spacebar after a period (full stop). Raised in Africa and having been trained in touch-typewriting, all my previous essays had double spacing after a period. However, given the fact that word processors justify spaces in-between fonts, the resource states that only one space is required after any punctuation in all EUCLID essays (EUCLID 2019, 18). Nevertheless, from experience, the use of single space after a period when using justified margin presents inconsistency in spacing but when used in left-based margin, it is constant. I particularly appreciated receiving this information very early in this course, as it is one of those pitfalls that have eluded my attention over the years.

b) Use of Punctuation within a Quotation

Determining whether to have punctuation within or outside a quotation mark is a subtle difficulty that I have noticed with many inexperienced writers like me. This difficulty is probably a result of undetermined style. I have seen myself entangled in this difficulty on a few occasions. Similarly, using comma at the end of a list before the conjunction ‘and’ or ‘or’ has been controversial among scholars (EUCLID 2019, 20). This controversy has been put to rest by the coursepack for EUCLID scholars.

c) Inconsistencies in Proofreading the Coursepack

Although a notice is given early in the coursepack concerning intentional errors in punctuation, context, spelling, et cetera, there are other errors noted in the material that appears to have been unaccounted for. For example, on page 20, examples 1 and 2 were same words, same punctuations; but they were supposed to be contrasted to show acceptable use of comma in a list. Another seeming error is the discussion of “Important Reminders” under a main chapter heading that was supposed to discuss literature review in preparing an essay (EUCLID 2019, 17). This appears to be a drift considering that the previous chapters were discussing preparations for writing a good essay. At this point, the reader is confused as to whether this was an intentional deviation from context. In any case, if these errors were deliberately inserted for teaching purposes, then the point is well made because they catch the reader’s attention.

On the other hand, a notable omission to the coursepack is the use of semicolon in EUCLID essays. This was either not discussed or it eluded me. Similarly, the RP template has a consistent page number/heading centered on all pages contrary to the requirement of having first page centered at the bottom and other pages numbered at the top right (EUCLID 2019, 50). Is it left for the students to adjust the template to meet this expectation? That is a lingering question for clarification.

3) CONCLUSION

Studying the EUCLID ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack for Period 1 has exposed me to the difficulties and expectations of the papers submitted for doctorate level assignments. Although some of the requirements were already known, there are some that were either new or helped to clarify some lingering doubts. Overall, having a foregleam of the intensity of the writings helps to prepare the mind for the doctoral program challenges as it is expected to be progressively difficult.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.